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Development and FEA of a Custom-Designed Bumper Beam for Ford Focus

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INFO

Technical note

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Abstract

This research presents the design and simulation process of an improved tubular crash bar for a Ford Focus vehicle. The primary objective of the development was to create an optimized structure that provides adequate space for a high-performance intercooler, while offering enhanced mechanical protection compared to simpler aftermarket tubular frames. The solution involves an integrated, forward-protruding supplementary tubular profile that functions as the primary energy-absorbing zone without obstructing the free flow of air into the engine compartment. The LS-DYNA software analysis of the CAD models designed in Solid Edge clearly validated the success of the concept: the improved design reduced the maximum equivalent stress by approximately 9% (from 584 MPa to 531 MPa). Furthermore, it reacted to the frontal impact in a third of the time compared to the base model (0.52 s instead of 1.56 s), thereby protecting the sensitive components of the vehicle's front end much more effectively.

Overview of the Vehicle Laboratory Infrastructure

Modern engineering education is unimaginable without high-level practical training that meets industrial standards. Keeping this principle in mind, the establishment of the Vehicle Research Center represented a huge step forward and a milestone in the life of the Faculty of Engineering at the University of Debrecen. The primary goal of the facility is to build a bridge between the complex theoretical knowledge taught at the university and the reality of the automotive industry, equipping future engineers with up-to-date knowledge and practical experience [3]. The infrastructure and equipment of the Center are aligned with state-of-the-art industrial requirements. The laboratories [4] also house, among other things, industrial KUKA robots [2], which enable the research and mastery of modern automation and manufacturing technology processes.

Figure 1: Robotics laboratory [1]

In the spaces specifically designed for automotive engineering and diagnostic tasks, professional car lifts and inspection pits are also available to students and researchers. These tools are essential for the comprehensive examination of motor vehicles, as they allow for the physical inspection, maintenance, and test preparation of the vehicles' chassis, suspension, and underbody components [5].

From an educational perspective, the significance of the Vehicle Research Center is invaluable. For the students of the Faculty of Engineering, this is not merely a research laboratory, but a real practical base where concepts designed in the classroom and in simulation software can also be examined in physical reality [6]. The practical time spent here and the work conducted with the state-of-the-art equipment significantly broaden the students' horizons, providing tangible engineering experience that represents an outstanding competitive advantage in the labor market [3] [7].

Figure 2: Automotive Research Center

Introduction

One of the most critical elements of the passive safety system in modern motor vehicles is the bumper reinforcement (crash bar). Its primary function is to absorb the kinetic energy generated during low-speed collisions (typically in parking or urban traffic), thereby protecting the expensive chassis rails and sensitive components in the engine compartment from permanent damage. However, in the case of performance-oriented vehicles, such as the Ford Focus [8] which serves as the basis for this paper, solid factory steel reinforcements often represent a compromise. During the tuning and performance enhancement of vehicles, replacing the factory component with an aftermarket tubular structure is almost an essential step [9]. There are several practical reasons for this: the thinner-walled tubular design results in significant weight reduction in the front of the car, and the more compact size drastically increases the available space. This gain in space allows for the installation of an increased volume, high-performance charge air cooler (intercooler) [10]. In addition, the optimized, cylindrical profile does not obscure the radiators, allowing much more air to flow into the engine compartment, not to mention that when viewed through the open grille, it aesthetically gives the vehicle a much more aggressive, sporty appearance.

Although the simpler tubular crash bars available on the market save space, they often underperform from a crash safety perspective. The aim of this assignment was to design an improved crash bar that combines the benefits of tuning with enhanced mechanical protection [11]. The essence of my design concept is that, compared to the base models found on the market, I integrated an extra tubular profile at the very front of the structure. I positioned this supplementary element in such a way that it does not obstruct the air flow at all and does not take away useful space from the intercooler. At the same time, in the event of a frontal bump, this protruding tube is the first to absorb the impact force, much more effectively protecting the expensive cooling units and the front of the vehicle from damage. A further advantage is that this more spatial, complex structure aesthetically enhances the front of the vehicle significantly, eliminating the visual impression of simple, single-tube solutions [12].

The 3D parametric modeling, as well as the design of the connection points and the frame structure, were carried out in Solid Edge software. In order to mechanically verify the justification and the improved energy-absorbing capacity of the developed model, I tested both the base and the improved models in the LS-DYNA finite element simulation software.

Theoretical Background

Passive Safety Systems

The task of passive safety systems begins at the critical moment when an accident becomes unavoidable. Their primary goal is the controlled absorption of the kinetic energy generated during a collision and the preservation of the passenger compartment's (survival space) integrity, thereby minimizing the deceleration forces acting on the passengers and the risk of injuries. The passive protection of a modern motor vehicle constitutes a complex, interdependent system. The coordinated operation of the individual elements will

determine the outcome of the collision, as their effects add up in forming the ultimate protection. Although common parlance refers to the entire front section as the "bumper," the outer plastic cover primarily serves an aerodynamic and aesthetic function. The crash bar and the crashbox are the most important primary load-bearing and energy-absorbing elements of the vehicle's front end [10].

LS-DYNA

LS-DYNA [13] is a finite element simulation software widely used in the automotive industry for the virtual simulation of crash tests and collisions. It is so widespread in engineering use because the software is capable of realistically modeling even the most complex structural behaviors. Thus, the component itself can be tested before manufacturing a physical prototype of the part or structural element. However, it must be taken into account that there are discrepancies between real and virtual tests, though preliminary virtual tests can help immensely in the initial design processes. We can input a vast amount of properties into the software, such as the dimensions of the element, its material type, and the forces acting upon it. This way, we can obtain various measurement data, which can later be compared with the measurement data of the real model. From the various measurement data obtained this way, we can observe the differences in the testing values [14]. This software provides great assistance in understanding the behavior of the crash bar during the collision process and in the development of its structure. Therefore, I will utilize this software for the comparison of the result values obtained for the crash bars.

Figure 3: LS-DYNA software in use

Creation of Models and Simulations

Modell Design

I used Solid Edge software to build the 3D CAD model of the improved crash bar. The choice was justified by two main factors: on the one hand, the program's transparent interface excellently supports the design of complex tubular frames, and on the other hand, I gained the deepest practical experience with it during my university studies [15].

Base Modell

As the first step of the development and optimization process, it was necessary to build a reference model. This base model represents the geometric and structural characteristics of typical aftermarket tuning bumper reinforcements currently available on the market.

Figure 4: Crash bar base model

The geometry of the model is built from three main structural units, which are as follows:

1. Mounting plates: Flat plate components located at the two edges of the structure, which provide the connection to the vehicle's factory chassis rails. The position of the 4-4 holes formed on the plates matches the mounting points of the original crumple zones.

Figure 5: Base model mounting element

2. Main cross tube: The curved tube profile in the upper position that forms the backbone of the structure. The bending radii and the extent of the protrusion were chosen so that the tube safely bypasses the increased-size charge air cooler (intercooler), while still fitting completely under the outer plastic bumper cover.

Figure 6: Base model longitudinal dimension

3. Lower support tubes: Straight tube sections located between the main tube and the lower part of the mounting plates. Their primary task is to secure the main crossmember and to increase the bending and torsional stiffness of the structure in the event of frontal or asymmetric loads.

Figure 7: Base model support tube dimensions

Improved Model

I integrated an additional, forward-protruding frontal tube profile into the main crossmember of the base model. This extra element has a positive protrusion along the longitudinal axis of the vehicle, meaning it is physically positioned further forward compared to the main load-bearing frame.

Figure 8: Improved model

This positioning has a critical role in vehicle dynamics and passive safety. Because this supplementary tube arch is on the outermost part, it functions as the primary contact point during a frontal collision. At the

moment of impact, this profile receives the primary force, thereby transforming the structure into a two-stage energy-absorbing zone. The plastic deformation of the protruding tube arch absorbs a significant portion of the kinetic energy even before the load reaches the main tube, and through it, the vehicle's chassis rails. This structural design comes with a dual advantage: on the one hand, it significantly reduces the peak force acting on the main frame and the chassis, and on the other hand, it creates a physical buffer zone. This physical buffer zone guarantees that during a low-speed bump, only the primary tube arch deforms, thus leaving the components located directly behind the crash bar intact. In addition, the structure retained its open nature, so aerodynamically, air can continue to flow unhindered towards the cooling system.

Figure 9: Improved model main dimensions

Creation of Simulation

After designing the models, the next step was to properly configure the simulation program. For this purpose, as I mentioned earlier, I used the LS-Dyna software, which is perfectly suitable for simulating these kinds of deformation processes. Proper configuration includes, among other things, setting the parameters, specifying the material properties of the model, and running the simulation with the appropriate settings. This ensures that both of my models are tested under the same conditions. Because this is the only way I can later compare the obtained results and values with each other. While using the software, I paid close attention to ensuring that every parameter is in the appropriate SI unit and that the parameters themselves match in every case. This ensured the proper execution and reliability of the simulations so that they can be reproducible.

Figure 10: Models in LS-Dyna

Figure 13 shows the simulation parameters that I used for both models. These determine with what values, parameters, and in what manner the simulations run [16].

Name	Count
BOUNDARY	2
PRESCRIBED_MOTION_RIGID	1
SPC_SET	1
CONTACT	2
AUTOMATIC_SINGLE_SURFACE	1
AUTOMATIC_SURFACE_TO_SURFACE	1
CONTROL	3
HOURGLASS	1
TERMINATION	1
TIMESTEP	1
DATABASE	3
ASCII_option	2
BINARY_D3PLOT	1
DEFINE	1
CURVE	1
ELEMENT	23139
SHELL	22139
SOLID	1000

KEYWORD	1
KEYWORD	1
MAT	2
003-PLASTIC_KINEMATIC	1
020-RIGID	1
NODE	23344
NODE	23344
PART	2
PART	2
SECTION	2
SHELL	1
SOLID	1
SET	1
NODE_LIST	1
TITLE	1
TITLE	1

Figure 11: List of LS-Dyna settings

Regarding material settings, Plastic Kinematic is the most important for us, which is the most frequently used metallic material model. This determines how the crash bar reacts to deformation in the given simulation. It is capable of describing the elastic-plastic behavior of metallic materials, and the material properties of the crash bar must also be specified within this setting. The material used in both simulations is steel in all cases, the material properties of which can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Material properties of simulation steel

Plastic Kinematic setting designation	Properties	Values
RO	Density (kg/m ³)	7850
PR	Poisson's ratio	0.3
E	Young's modulus (MPa)	200000
SIGY	Yield strength (MPa)	250
ETAN	Tangent modulus (GPa)	1.45

Rigid is essentially a special setting describing a material model that we use on rigid bodies. More precisely, in such cases, these bodies do not deform; they are only endowed with a specific property, such as displacement. In my simulation, the compression plate will receive this property, so this body can only move and collide. With the Rigid setting in this case, only the density needs to be specified, as it does not deform.

Evaluation of Simulations

Figure 12: Final simulations

Placing the deformation figures of the simulations side by side, it can be determined at first glance that the crumpling of the two models is almost identical. In the case of both the base model and the improved version, the main cross tube was pressed in with a similar curve and extent under the effect of the load. It is important to highlight, however, that although the resulting deformation is geometrically very similar, we know from the analyzed stress and pressure data that the structure reached this state in a completely different way. While in the base model this bending occurred suddenly, accompanied by high tensile stresses, in my improved model the extra tube, functioning as a physical buffer, absorbed the load earlier in time and more evenly. So, even though the two "collapsed" tubular frames look almost identical, the model I designed reached this final deformation state much more in a controlled manner, dampening the sudden force effects.

Y-stress

Figure 13: Y-stress tests

Based on the longitudinal normal stress (Y-stress) figures obtained from the simulations, it is clearly visible that my improved model fulfilled the preliminary expectations. The results showed that by integrating the extra tube, I managed to reduce the maximum tensile stress responsible for sudden material tearing from 281 MPa to 262 MPa, which enables much more predictable energy absorption during the collision. At the same time, the maximum compressive stress resulting from the frontal impact increased (from 277 MPa to 297 MPa), and as I planned, it concentrated directly on the supplementary profile I added. This stress redistribution validates the basic idea of my assignment: the first extra tube truly acts as a dedicated crumple zone, absorbs the load first, and thus successfully relieves the main frame behind it.

von Mises stress

Figure 14: von Mises stress tests

The comparison of the stress distribution contour plots clearly validates the advantage of the improved geometry. While in the reference model the maximum equivalent (von Mises) stress reached 584 MPa at the same moment of the collision, in the case of the model with the integrated supplementary tube arch this value decreased to 531 MPa. This approximately 9% stress reduction means that the load occurring during plastic deformation is distributed much more evenly across the structure. By mitigating local stress peaks, the risk of early, premature tearing of the material is significantly reduced, which is essential for guaranteeing stable and continuous energy absorption.

Pressure

Figure 15: Pressure tests

At first glance, the maximum values on the pressure contour plots are almost identical in both cases. However, this does not mean that the two models behave in the same way. If we look at the time the maximum pressure develops, the difference is huge: while in the base model this peak value only develops at the $t=1.56$ time instant, the model I developed, equipped with the supplementary tube, already reaches this at $t=0.52$. This proves my concept: the protruding extra tube reacts to the impact much sooner, begins energy absorption faster, thus we gain time and distance so that the expensive cooling components do not get damaged.

Conclusion

The simulation results clearly validated the justification of the geometric modification I introduced. Based on the stress figures, by integrating the extra tube, the tensile stress responsible for sudden material tearing significantly decreased, and the load was distributed more evenly. In addition, the pressure curves proved that the new structure reacts to the frontal impact in a third of the time compared to the base model. The protruding profile I designed thereby functions as a primary, dedicated crumple zone: it absorbs the initial kinetic energy, breaks down the stress peaks, and protects the valuable cooling components as a physical buffer without hindering the free flow of air entering the engine compartment.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding authors.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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